

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE FORMATION OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL QUALITIES OF THE CHARACTER OF CHILDREN IN THE FAMILY

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Abstract. *This article explores the psychological aspects of the formation of character and its spiritual and moral qualities, scientific, theoretical and practical foundations for educating a spiritually and physically mature generation. In this regard, the opinions of thinkers and psychologists were used as a methodological basis. The question of the influence of the teacher and the educator on the upbringing of individual traits of the child's character only through the team and the formation of the spiritual and moral characteristics of the child's character in the family is highlighted.*

Keywords: *character, character traits, determination, courage, willpower, generosity, spiritual, physical fitness, upbringing, decency, honesty.*

Raising a spiritual and physically harmonious generation - an issue of not only national extinction, but also of universal importance – is such a noble goal for all fraternal peoples born and raised in our multinational Homeland, spreading veins. At this point, national and universal values, the best traditions of our rich spiritual heritage and the new talents that are being formed unite, become a powerful factor in upbringing.

The features of the formation of character and its spiritual and moral qualities, scientific-theoretical, practical foundations were studied by psychologists from foreign and Commonwealth countries. From psychologist scientists R.Menton, C.A.Horney, E.Fromm, Krechmer, Sheldon, Kettell, Feofrast, among others, studied character traits in every possible way. He also received a B. from psychologist scientists from the Commonwealth countries. G. Ananov, A.A.Bodalev, V.N.Myasichev, V.V. Davidov, A.G. Kovalev, Asmolovs studied the features of the formation of character and its spiritual and moral qualities and other aspects of it. In the teaching of scientists of Uzbekistan, the study of the problem of character and its features is analyzed.

With the character problem E.G.Goziev, M.G.Davletshin, V.A.Tokareva, M.M.The mamatovs conducted comparative studies. The history of the teachings about the character goes back to the distant past. In particular, Arastu and Plato had proposed to determine the character of a person by face. The opinions of thinkers, psychologist scientists in this regard serve as a methodological basis. Abu Nasr Farabi of the allivkkirs, in his work "the city of fertile people", comments on good and evil, saying that good brings happiness, and evil does not bring happiness to a person. He challenges people to be a man of courage, generosity, chastity, loyalty, courage, perseverance, independent thinking, experienced, decency. Farabi's thoughts go about the formation of positive qualities in a person's character .

Although the problem of character is widely studied in psychology, Haley needs a lot of theoretical research and Applied Research. Husayn Ecclesiastes says: "the target of a beautiful character is ten things: the first target is good; the second is dishonest; the third is not to look for guilt from another person; the fourth is to start it on a good path if a person also sees an indecent

act; the fifth is to accept his apology if a person apologizes for confessing his guilt; the sixth is; the ninth is to bring out the oppressors of the needy; the tenth is to be gentle and humble" .

As great thinkers say, morality is such a mirror in which not only the external appearance of a person, but also the inner world is visible. The simpler the basis of their characterology, the more bizarre the hypothesis lay.

In the appearance of a person, it was recommended to find a sign of similarity with some kind of animal, and then look at his character as exactly the same as that of this animal.

Situations like this always employ the self-discipline of an individual's own character and the re-education of one's own character. That is, a person is responsible for his character and his qualities from a certain age. In the upbringing of his character, a person must first of all foresee his good qualities. Confessing to his shortcomings begins to lose his shortcomings. Since each nation has its own characteristics and mentality, the national, spiritual heritage of ancestors is the main resource for progress and perspective. A nation that does not follow the path of development on the basis of its own basis, in perspective, loses its identity . In this case, it is necessary to consider the development of the nation, relying on its own basis, to follow. Such lofty, spiritually worthy features:

1. Tenacity. The ability to make drastic changes in life, willingly accepting possible consequences.
2. Courage. A quality that a person can do something, despite fear.
3. Willpower. The ability to resist momentary Temptations in favor of a prosperous future.
4. Generosity. When a person is easily separated from his resources for the benefit of another. While generosity is usually associated with money, there may also be other resources, such as time. Sometimes the latter is even more appreciated by loved ones. In general, it can be generous in a broad and narrow sense.
5. Purposefulness. This quality is especially positive when a person and his immediate environment are striving for the same results. Then he becomes the leader, thanks to him, all the members of the group begin to live better. Purposefulness can be destructive only if a person is focused on his own goals, since he does not take into account the interests of other people.
6. Decency, honesty. This includes the absence of a dog to hide something from his loved ones, openness to them.
7. Empathy. The ability to feel and act on the feelings of another person.

The formation of spiritual and moral qualities of a person's character is a complex process, on the one hand, education depends on the educational environment, and on the other, on the individual characteristics and interpersonal relationships of the individual.

Due to such motivational power of character traits, a person often acts contrary to objective conditions and applies completely non-objective methods of action. As character traits are encouraged to act in a certain way in opposition to parts of action, and sometimes to circumstances, they are better manifested in life difficult moments, and this is an important task of raising a character, as well as a harmonious generation. Personality traits such as clairvoyance, criticality, understanding, observability are included in intellectual, cheerful, kind emotional - volitional qualities.

Despite differing definitions of character in Psychology, its main characters fall in line with the emphasis. For example, a person's attitude towards society is his main sign. The quality that helps a person to live and benefits people is considered positive. Frequent family conflicts, parental

discord, and corporal punishment of adolescents naturally lead to changes in their behavior. Children and adolescents raised in such an environment are characterized by excitability, irritability, lack of self-control, jealousy, dissatisfaction, hostility, fear, loss of self-confidence, loneliness, indifference. Each of these qualities negatively affects the mental and personal qualities of the child, the formation and mental development of the child, as well as willpower. Parents were role models of hamisha for their children. Children follow and are proud of their parents above all. Parents will always be an example for their children if a good psychological climate is decided in the family. Young children in the family, first of all, pay attention to their parents, follow them, are proud of them. When a good psychological environment is decided in the family, young children become less stressed, able to correctly assess their strengths and weaknesses, be able to mobilize their energy in the pursuit of goals. Self-confidence will help the child become independent among the team and peers. Unlike children in a depressive state, the social behavior of children of this character will be positive in nature, it will be given less to the influence of its own internal conflicts, openly and directly express its thoughts. Children who tend to be affected by depression are instead passive, have no strong self-confidence, are more susceptible to the influence of others, are more inclined to express personal feedback. While the family is dominated by attitudes of an authoritarian (based on parents, adults, passing their judgment) nature, children who are usually growing up in such an environment are easily anxious, restless, frustration symptoms are observed, sociuu manifests itself passively in life (relationships). In a family environment, where interaction is based on the care, kindness, demanding of parents, adults about the little ones, such children actively behave in social life (relationships), will react in a positive psyche towards those around them. The main types of deviant behavior that can be observed in young children and adolescents are as follows: does not welcome obedience to discipline. A rebellious attitude towards the social order. Ignores social orders. Delinkvent behavior. The tendency to violate the norms of the right decided in society will be strongly expressed. The first type of deviant behavioural sentence can include a tendency to break the order and discipline established in the educational space in particular. Usually children with this temperament try to break classes, refuse to fulfill teacher assignments. The following can be included in the sentence of (antisocial) behavior contrary to generally accepted social norms:

- refusal of study and socially useful labor activity;
- getting into sexual contact early in age;
- excessive abstinence in sexual relations;
- obsession with alcohol consumption;

In such situations, it is necessary to thoroughly study the character of young people who have entered the path of crime. A mistake made in their education and it is necessary to identify shortcomings and try to correct them.

The psycho-preventive measures carried out are aimed at providing social support in the psychological and pedagogical sphere in order to protect adolescents from the negative effects of individuals around them, namely:

- a) family, neighborhood, study group, classroom and pedagogical Community, Media;
- b) consists in optimizing educational and educational conditions that affect the main edges of adolescent interpersonal relationships.

In the conclusion urn, it is worth saying that a properly organized educational process can educate and correct character accentuation.

Each teacher and educator can achieve positive results in the upbringing of certain qualities of the child's character, affecting only through the team.

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